

Design, Synthesis and Biological Screening of New Pyrazoline Derivatives†

V. S. JOLLY* and MANISH PATHAK

Chemical Laboratories,
Government Model Science College,
Gwalior-474 009

Manuscript received 28 January 1991, accepted 17 May 1991

PYRAZOLINES¹ and amino compounds² are known for their activities. In view of potential pharmacological value, the new pyrazoline derivatives are designed to contain COCH₂CONH group at position-1 and cyanoethylamino moiety at position-3. Selection of β- and γ-methyl group to N atom is designed on the usual occurrence of this group in some important amino acids. Synthetic sequence has been outlined in Scheme 1.

R = *o*-CH₃, *m*-CH₃
Scheme 1

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer.

N-Cyanoethyl-*N*-*o*/*m*-methylaniline³ and malonanilic acid hydrazides⁴ were prepared as reported.

† Presented at the 27th Annual Convention of Chemists, 1990 at Bodhgaya (Abstr. no. ORG(OS)-12).

***N*-Cinnamoyl-*N*-cyanoethyl-*N*-*o*-methylaniline**: A mixture of *N*-cyanoethyl-*N*-*o*-methylaniline (0.01 mol), cinnamoyl chloride (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (2 g) was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and left overnight. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol as white crystalline solid (56.0%), m.p. 160° (Found: N, 9.52; O, 5.47. C₁₉H₁₈N₂O requires: N, 9.65; O, 5.51%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 660 (C=C), 1 650 (C=O) and 2 240 cm⁻¹ (C≡N).

***N*-Cinnamoyl-*N*-cyanoethyl-*N*-*m*-methylaniline**: It was synthesised as above yielding light brown crystals (62%), m. p. 105° (Found: N, 9.48; O, 5.49. C₁₉H₁₈N₂O requires: N, 9.65; O, 5.51%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 660 (C=C), 1 650 (C=O) and 2 240 cm⁻¹ (C≡N).

1-(Anilinomalonyl)-3-(*N*-*o*-methylanilino-*N*-β-cyanoethylamino)-5-phenylpyrazoline: A mixture of *N*-cinnamoyl-*N*-cyanoethyl-*N*-*o*-methylaniline (0.001 mol), malonanilic acid hydrazide (0.001 mol) in dioxane (2 ml) and glacial acetic acid (1 drop) was refluxed for 5 h. The resulting solid was washed with hot ethanol to yield white crystals (0.185 g, 40.0%), m.p. 245° (Found: N, 14.92; O, 6.77. C₂₈H₂₇N₅O₃ requires: N, 15.15; O, 6.88%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 590 (C=N), 1 650 (C=O), 3 100 (NH) and 2 240 cm⁻¹ (C≡N).

Other pyrazolines were synthesised by the same procedure (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE PYRAZOLINES*

Compd. no.	R ₁	Yield (%)	M p. °C	Mol. formula
R = <i>o</i> -CH ₃				
1.	H	40	245	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₃
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	32	230	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
3.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	30	220	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	38	248	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
5.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	36	245	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
6.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	40	244	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
7.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	32	210	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
8.	<i>o</i> -Cl	32	246	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ ClN ₅ O ₃
9.	<i>m</i> -Cl	30	258	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ ClN ₅ O ₃
10.	<i>p</i> -Cl	36	222	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ ClN ₅ O ₃
R = <i>m</i> -CH ₃				
11.	H	34	230	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₃
12.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	32	218	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
13.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	40	252	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
14.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	38	207	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
15.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	22	227	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
16.	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	42	210	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
17.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	32	240	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃
18.	<i>o</i> -Cl	33	260	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ ClN ₅ O ₃
19.	<i>m</i> -Cl	40	270	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ ClN ₅ O ₃
20.	<i>p</i> -Cl	36	224	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ ClN ₅ O ₃

* All compounds (white solid) gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Anti-HIV screening: Some of pyrazoline derivatives were tested for antiviral activity for AIDS which involved susceptible human host cells. Compound sl. no. 1 (Table 1) showed 46.93% control at 7.72 × 10⁻⁵ M dose and the response of compound sl. no. 14 was 27.23% at 7.50 × 10⁻⁵ M dose on the infected plates. The other pyrazoline derivatives did not show significant anti-HIV activity.

Anticancer activity: Compounds sl. nos. 1, 14 and 17 were tested for anticancer (*in vitro* P 388

Leukemia) activity, and the activity of all were found low by National Cancer Institute on many tumour cell line subpanels.

Antibacterial activity: 12 pyrazoline derivatives were screened for antibacterial activity against gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and *S. albus* and gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas piosineus* applying agar plate disc diffusion technique⁵. Compounds sl. nos. 13 and 15 showed higher activity (13–14 mm zone of inhibition) against *S. albus*. In comparison to others, the following compounds showed higher activities: sl. nos. 13 and 15 against *S. albus* (13–14 mm zone of inhibition); sl. no. 10 against *S. aureus* (11–12 mm); sl. no. 9 against *E. coli* (13–14 mm); sl. no. 10 against *P. piosineus* (11–12 mm).

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to Director, National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, Maryland, U. S. A. for anti-HIV and anticancer activities and to Director, D. R. D. E., Gwalior, for spectral analysis. The authors are also grateful to Dr. A. K. Shrivastava for the help rendered and to Mr. B. B. Pandey, G. R. Medical College, Gwalior, for antibacterial activity.

References

1. G. D. THORN, *Phytopathology*, 1961, **51**, 77; J. W. SOWELL, A. J. DERRIC, M. E. FREEMAN and J. J. KOSH, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1981, **70**, 135; M. STAMPER and B. F. AVCOCK *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2786; M. SADO and C. SAKAE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1989, **110**, 75490; T. M. STEVENSONS, *Ch:m. Abstr.*, 1989, **110**, 75489; T. C. SHARMA, M. M. BOKADIA and N. J. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 228; H. G. GARG and V. ARORA, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1972, **61**, 130.
2. RUSSELL and HUTCHINGS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 3763.
3. S. A. HEININGER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 1213.
4. B. S. RATHORE and P. I. ITTYERAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 595.
5. R. S. VARMA and S. A. IMAM, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1973, **13**, 45.